

FORMS AND METHODS OF ORGANIZING POTTERY COURSES

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Abstract. *The active forms of learning in this article are lecture-dialogue, problem lecture, consultation, conversation, summary, excursion, business game, discussion, round table, conference. Information is given about active methods of conducting classes: visual aids, self-education lessons, problem-based learning, practical assignment, problem assignment, analysis of specific situations, dialogue, discussions.*

Keywords: *training, visual aids, self-education lessons, problem-based learning, practical assignment, problem assignment, analysis of specific situations, dialogue, discussion, polemic.*

In modern pedagogy, the concept of problem-based teaching was formed, generalized for a group of teaching methods, i.e. - presenting a problem, partial search and research. The common feature of these methods is the independent activity of the student to solve the problem, in the process of which new knowledge is acquired, skills and abilities are formed, experience is accumulated, and a certain system of interests is formed. The active role of the student in the learning process stimulates all mental and cognitive operations, especially thinking and imagination.

The difference between the methods included in the problem-based teaching system is determined by the level of participation of the teacher and student in the formulation of problem tasks and solving problem situations:

- problematic presentation - in which the teacher himself creates a problem, creates a problematic situation, reveals the contradiction inherent in it, shows the course of solving it;
- partial search - in which the teacher poses a problem, creates a problematic situation, and students solve it independently or with the help of the teacher;
- research method - in which the teacher gives a creative task and the students solve it independently, identify the problem, identify the contradictions inherent in it, formulate the task and look for ways to solve it. The use of this method implies the highest level of creative competence of the student and is the main type of problem-based education.

Forms of education in pedagogy are types of training. They make it possible to organize the educational process in accordance with the needs of students and the tasks set within the educational and cognitive activity. It is necessary to pay special attention to the choice of the appropriate form to achieve the masad, because it mainly determines the efficiency of the process.

Forms and methods of training are the following ways and methods of stimulating influence:

- mental activity;
- show a creative approach to finding ways to improve the quality of education;
- putting the acquired knowledge into practice.

A necessary condition for effective use of the forms and methods of conducting classes is the high theoretical training and methodological skills of the teacher.

Forms and methods are related to each other. On the one hand, forms are filled with specific content using methods, and on the other hand, forms influence the choice of methods.

The methods of conducting classes are divided into the following:

According to the source of acquiring knowledge, skills, qualifications:

- oral;
- visual;
- practical.

According to the level of activity and independence of students:

- explanatory and illustrative;
- information;
- partial search systems;
- problematic;
- research.

The form of the training is the educational system of the educational institution, its internal structure, and a certain procedure for conducting it. Active forms of training are public discussion of problems aimed at correct understanding of the content of the subject, active interaction of the audience, organization of an educational process designed for the exchange of ideas between them.

Active forms of training: lecture-dialogue, problem lecture, consultation, conversation, report, excursion, business game, discussion, roundtable, conference.

Active methods of training: visual aids, self-education lessons, problem-based learning, practical assignment, problem assignment, analysis of specific situations, dialogue, debate, polemic.

Active forms of training include:

Lecture – it is a type of public speech during which the speaker communicates live with the audience, reveals the system of ideas about a certain topic, phenomenon, helps the audience to understand the problem and come to a certain conclusion.

The most used lecture types: lecture-dialogue, problem lecture.

The following are the most important requirements for the lecture: scientific, high theoretical level, relevance to life, clarity, comprehensibility, scientific evidence.

Consulting – this is the teacher's explanation of a complex and relevant theoretical question, problem; a necessary condition for effective independent study of the theory and problem.

Types of consultation: personal, group, commentary, on specific issues.

Talking – a specially organized conversation on this topic. Its purpose is to help by exchanging ideas for a better understanding of the problem under study.

The main tasks of the conversation: during training - help in self-education, getting acquainted with the methods of practical application of the acquired knowledge, during testing of knowledge - have you read the recommended literature? Did you complete the practical assignment? Does the student know how to apply the acquired knowledge in practice? questions are answered.

Conference is a form of collective study and discussion of current theoretical and scientific-practical problems.

The types of conferences and the issues discussed in them are as follows:

theoretical conference - current problems of the theory of teaching and upbringing;

scientific-methodical - psychological-pedagogical problems; issues of teaching and upbringing methodology, practical use of the most effective forms and methods of work; generalization of pedagogical experience and issues of education and training, latest achievements of pedagogic science;

scientific-practical - analysis of content, forms and methods of work; consideration of current issues of educational work in a particular educational institution.

At the conference, it is recommended to invite the authors of scientific works (projects), theses, lectures, which were considered the best during the class discussion, to give a speech.

Round table is a form of collective discussion of current issues of science, theory and practice. The participants should be introduced in advance to the composition of the invitations, the issues to be discussed, so that they can participate in the conversation.

Discussion – this is a public oral discussion of a controversial issue, in which reports on the issue and, as a rule, opponents' speeches are heard. The topic of discussion can be acute theoretical problems, current issues, ethical problems, acute articles in periodicals, etc. It is important to think carefully about the text of the issues to be discussed, to give them a problematic character and to familiarize the participants with them in advance.

In the final words, the participants should draw attention to the valuable and useful things that the discussion gave to its participants and summarize the results.

Business game – this is a form of activity that simulates certain practical situations, one of the means of activating the educational process. Types of business games and the goals they achieve: mastering certain skills and competencies; assessment of knowledge and skills acquired by students; development and improvement of new or certain methods of a certain activity.

Elements of preparing and holding a business game:

1. Imitation object or game object.
2. Purpose, tasks.
3. Scope of results.
4. Roles and functions of players.
5. Rules, game conditions.
6. Games and role-playing are the result of cooperation.
7. Documentary support.
8. Ratings.

Excursion – visual learning is one of the most effective forms of educational work. Excursions are recommended after studying the course and topic.

Excursions can be conducted before studying the subject. They guide students to issues that need to be addressed in the classroom. Before going on an excursion, students should set specific educational tasks, familiarize them with the excursion plan.

Visual aids – Visual aids and technical training manuals used in the educational process can significantly increase the effectiveness of perception.

Types of visual aids:

Natural production objects.

Visual: 1) figurative - photo, picture, poster; 2) conditional-schematic - map, diagram, scheme, table.

Technical means of teaching: 1) mass media - television, film; 2) local technical means of teaching: screen, sound, screen-sound. Visual aids should be used correctly as follows: reduce the

time of studying the problem by 20-25%; improve the understanding of the problem by 25%; increase the level of memorization of educational material by 35%.

Visual aids for training are selected in advance. At the same time, the teacher not only demonstrates visualization tools, but also explains their content and pays attention to details.

Visual aids do not replace the teacher, but only complement his speech. It is necessary to observe a sense of proportion in relation to the number of visual aids used, excessive interest in them can have a negative effect on the perception of new material.

Problem solving – this is a system of methods by which students acquire knowledge not in a ready form, but as a result of independent activity, as a result of solving educational problems. It helps to train the system of actions to independently solve cognitive tasks.

Levels of problematic education:

1. The teacher sets and formulates a problem, directs students to independently search for its solution.

2. The teacher only names the problem, and the students themselves formulate it and find a solution.

3. Students independently understand and formulate a problem, learn ways to solve it.

Methods of organizing problem-based education:

1. Problematic presentation of educational material.

2. Research interview, during which students solve educational problems under the guidance of the teacher.

3. Independent work of the search character.

An indispensable condition of problem-based education is the application of acquired knowledge to practical activities; learning to apply the acquired knowledge in certain conditions. The purpose of problem tasks should be to understand real problems theoretically, to search for ways to solve them in practice.

Dialog – it is a conversation, interview, exchange of ideas between two or more people in order to prove a certain idea or system of views. Dialogue is a non-dogmatic way of expressing ideas; debate, debate form; form of joint reflection.

The characteristics of dialogue as a method of training are as follows: unplanned communication; a lot of interrogative sentences; contextuality (semantic connection of dialogue parts with each other); undefined, free form of presentation of opinions, evidence; copies of interlocutors; situationality (relation to the situation under consideration).

Debate – this is one of the effective ways to discuss various issues and develop cognitive activity. Tasks of discussion: to determine the truth by comparing different points of view; justification and defense of one's ideas, views, positions; resolving conflicts in the dispute process; development of scientific views.

Discussion - collective discussion of controversial issues, finding ways to solve them; one of the ways to activate the educational process.

The topic of discussion: problems that arise as a reflection of the contrast between knowledge and ignorance, complete and incomplete knowledge, scientific and everyday knowledge, the ability and inability to apply knowledge in practice.

Rules of discussion: formulating one's thoughts clearly; dispute on the merits; the desire to establish the truth; respect the opponent's point of view; humility and self-criticism; behave. The

topic for discussion should be chosen keeping in mind the interests and requirements of the students.

Analysis of specific situations is one of the active methods of studying current problems and strengthening the connection between theory and practice. Types of situations: situations-illustrations; situations-exercises; situations-evaluation; problematic situations.

Content of situations: events or processes at the stage of development, change; emergence, sources and causes of development, deviation from the norm of any facts, events; actions or actions of certain persons involved in the situations under consideration.

A practical task is a type of independent work aimed at developing the skills and abilities to apply the acquired knowledge in practical activities. Forms of tasks: individual and collective.

The traditions of folk art should be the basis for the formation of the student's aesthetic ideas, as well as the development of his special abilities. One of the tasks of the teacher is to recognize these abilities, in particular, creativity, to direct them in the right direction, to give the basis of knowledge and skills for processing the selected material - clay. In order to effectively develop the creative competence of students, it is necessary to study in detail the specific characteristics of this material (clay) and its processing methods.

The modern technology of industrial production of ceramic products involves the use of complex equipment. One of the tasks of our experimental work is the development of clay processing techniques using mass materials, equipment and tools, as well as simple methods of making pottery products in the educational process.

Raw materials. One of the most important points in the production of pottery products is the preparation of raw material - clay. The success of the artist's idea and the quality of the product depend on how carefully the clay is prepared. Therefore, the demand for the selection and preparation of raw materials and materials increases. The selection of raw materials consists of several stages.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the characteristics of natural raw materials and technology of their processing, reliable ownership of equipment and equipment helps to effectively implement ideas and, as a result, is related to the development of creative competence.

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